

Welcome to the
13th International Society for Computational Biology
Student Council Symposium!

Organisers

Chair	Julien Fumey, French National Centre for Scientific Research - I2BC, France
Co-Chair	Mehedi Hassan, University of South Wales, United Kingdom
Organising Committee	Bart Cuypers, Institute of Tropical Medicine, Antwerp, Belgium Ben Siranosian, Broad Institute of MIT and Harvard, United States of America Aishwarya Alex Namasivayam, University of Luxembourg, Nazeefa Fatima, University of Huddersfield, United Kingdom Alexander Monzon, National University of Quilmes, Argentina
Advisor	Farzana Rahman, Chair, University of South Wales, United Kingdom Sayane Shome, Iowa State University, United States of America Dan DeBlasio, Carnegie Mellon University, United States of America R. Gonzalo Parra, Secretary, Max Planck Institute for Biophysical Chemistry, Germany Alex Salazar, Delft University of Technology, The Netherlands

First print, July 2017

Copyright © 2017 ISCB Student Council and contributing authors. All rights reserved.

This booklet was designed and edited by Ben Siranosian

Contents were prepared in in June 2017.

For latest updates please visit the symposium page at symposium.iscb.org

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. To view a copy of this license, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>. This booklet may be reproduced without permission in its original form.

Disclaimer

The ISCB Student Council has made all efforts to provide accurate information but does not guarantee the correctness of any information provided in this booklet. The ISCB Student Council is a committee of the International Society for Computational Biology (ISCB), which is incorporated as a 501(c)(3) non-profit corporation in the United States.

Welcome to the 13th ISCB Student Council Symposium

The ISCB Student Council is pleased to welcome you to the 13th edition of the International Society for Computational Biology Student Council Symposium in Prague, Czech Republic. After the success of previous Symposia, which took place in Orlando (2016), Dublin (2015), Boston (2014), Berlin (2013), Long Beach (2012), Vienna (2011), Boston (2010), Stockholm (2009), Toronto (2008), Vienna (2007), Fortaleza (2006), and Madrid (2005), we are thrilled to once again offer our delegates the opportunity to meet students and young scientists from all over the world. As usual, our primary goals are to promote the exchange of ideas and to foster the creation and strengthening of scientific social networks.

We are honored to have **Dr. Christine Orengo** (University College London, UK) and **Dr. Johannes Söding** from the Max Planck Institute for Biophysical Chemistry, Germany as keynote speakers at this year's Symposium. Their keynotes promise to be inspiring presentations of exceptional work relevant to everyone in the field. We are also very excited to have **Dr. Chris Cheadle's** team from Elsevier and **Dr. Fiona Nielsen** from Repositio.io to present some very pertinent topics to the symposium attendees.

We will start the Symposium with the keynote by Dr. Orengo. This will be followed by an ice breaking & networking session to provide the delegates a chance to get to know your peers in an informal and friendly way. Throughout the day we will hear **oral presentations** from a selection of **outstanding student abstracts** spanning a wide range of research areas.

Inspired by the success of our Orlando, 2016 edition, this year we will also have a selection of authors presenting flash-talks on their work. These shorter version oral presentations promise to be a great addition to the day.

In the evening, the **poster session** will offer exciting science in various domains, and give everybody a chance to discuss their research topics in more depth. Light refreshments will be offered during the poster reception session. Everyone in-

volved in the organization of this Symposium contributed significantly to make this event happen. Our volunteers have spent months preparing all aspect of this Symposium ranging from the invitation of keynote speakers, fundraising, advertising and organizing the peer-review process to more technical aspect like designing the website.

We encourage you to make the most out of this opportunity and to be very active in engaging other delegates, asking questions, discussing ideas and showcasing your own research. You can make this Symposium a starting point for fruitful future collaborations and another step towards a successful career in computational biology.

Enjoy your time in Prague!

Thank you

On Behalf of the organisers,

Julien Fumey, Student Council Symposium Chair

Mehedi Hassan, Student Council Symposium Co-Chair

Tweeting at the Symposium

Official Hashtag #SCS17

Follow us on **@iscbsc**

Contents

Program of the Day	1
Keynote Speakers	3
Sponsored Speakers	4
Thank You to Our Sponsors!	5
Session 1: Proteins, DNA, Sequences and Evolution	6
Session 2: Networks and 3D Interactions	9
Session 3: Modeling Cancer, Viruses and Diseases	13
Poster Presentations	22

Program of the Day

Time	Title	Page
8:30-9:00	Opening Remarks	
9:00-10:00	Keynote lecture: Looking for LUCA - and other evolutionary tales <u>Christine Orengo</u>	3
10:00-10:15	Ice Breaking Event	
10:15-10:45	Morning Coffee Break	
Oral presentation session 1: Proteins, DNA, Sequences and Evolution		
10:45-11:00	Determining the function of the apicomplexan 6-Cys/SRS protein family: a structural and evolutionary understanding of pathogen invasion <u>Eli Draizen</u>	6
11:00-11:15	scTree: reconstructing complex cellular lineage trees from single-cell RNA-seq data <u>Rodrigo Gonzalo Parra</u>	6
11:15-11:30	The impact of native state switching on protein sequence evolution <u>Avital Sharir-Ivry</u>	7
11:30-11:45	SequenceServer: a modern graphical user interface for BLAST <u>Anurag Priyam</u>	8
11:45-12:30	Sponsored talk by Elsevier: Pathway Studio hands-on session	
12:30-13:15	Lunch Break	
Oral presentation session 2: Networks and 3D Interactions		
13:15-13:30	Differential network analysis hints at revealing mechanism of actions of combined drug applications <u>Mohamed Hamed</u>	9
13:30-13:45	Reducing noise in Hi-C interaction matrices at restriction fragment resolution <u>Christopher JF Cameron</u>	9
13:45-13:50	Intervene: a tool for intersection and visualization of multiple gene or genomic region sets <u>Aziz Khan</u>	10
13:50-13:55	Modeling and Stochastic Simulation of Gene Regulatory Networks in <i>Escherichia coli</i> <u>Rodrigo Santibáñez</u>	10
13:55-14:00	Discovery of murine tissue specific regulatory drivers and their impact <u>Siddharth Sethi</u>	11
Oral presentation session 3: Modeling Cancer, Viruses and Diseases		
14:00-14:15	Logical modeling approaches as a proxy to analyze cardiovascular disease trajectories <u>Amel Bekkar</u>	12
14:15-14:30	Fidelity of contig spectra based community modelling for estimating viral diversity measures using metaviromes <u>Damayanthi Herath</u>	12
14:30-15:30	Keynote lecture: Sensitive protein sequence searching and clustering for the analysis of massive metagenomics datasets <u>Johannes Söeding</u>	3
15:30-15:50	Afternoon Coffee Break	

Continuation of session 3

15:50-16:05	Integrating diverse transcriptomic alterations to identify cancer-relevant genes and signatures <u>Natalie Davidson</u>	13
16:05-16:35	Sponsored talk by Fiona Nielsen of Repositive: A bioinformaticians spark which lead to a new platform for sharing genomic data	4
16:35-16:40	A comprehensive meta-analysis of the induced immediate early response reveals a conserved order of promoter activation <u>Annalaura Vacca</u>	13
16:40-16:45	Predicting abnormal circadian phenotypes in mouse <u>John Williams</u>	14
16:45-16:50	TOPSPIN: a novel algorithm to predict treatment specific survival in cancer <u>Joske Ubels</u>	15
16:50-16:55	Homology modeling in a dynamical world <u>Alexander Monzon</u>	15
16:55-17:00	Influence of temperature in the conformational change of zika virus e protein and its consequences in viral infectivity <u>Gabriela Muniz</u>	16
17:00-17:05	Mining CD8+ T-cell receptor patterns underlying immunogenic peptide recognition <u>Nicolas De Neuter</u>	16
17:05-17:10	CRISPys: gene family silencing using the CRISPR-Cas9 system <u>Gal Hyams</u>	17
17:10-17:15	Global proteomics profiling improves drug sensitivity prediction: results from a multi-omics, pan-cancer modeling approach <u>Mehreen Ali</u>	17
17:15-17:20	Computational proteogenomic identification of translated fusions and micro structural variations in cancer <u>Yen-Yi Lin</u>	18
17:20-17:25	Zippping and assembly with limited sets of constraints <u>Maryana Wanggren</u>	19
17:25-17:30	Computational methods for detection of loss of heterozygosity events and their diagnostic relevance for rare Mendelian disorders <u>Numrah Fadra</u>	19
17:30-18:00	Poster Session	
18:15-19:15	ISMB opening keynote: Reconstructing cellular circuits: from cells to tissues <u>Aviv Regev</u>	
20:15-Onwards	Networking Event	

Keynote Speakers

Dr. Christine Orengo is an expert in bioinformatics applied to protein structure and evolution. She is a Professor of Bioinformatics at University College London (UCL) and currently leads a research group focused on understanding how protein domains are conserved over evolutionary time and developing methods to predict protein function. Dr. Orengo began her career at UCL, where she was awarded a PhD in Biochemistry in 1984. She went on to work in industry for a short time, did a postdoc at the National Institute of Medical Research and eventually returned to UCL. Notably, her group developed The CATH Protein Structure Classification database in the mid 1990s, which still provides up-to-date information about the evolutionary relationships between protein domains.

Dr. Johannes Söding is an internationally recognized researcher in the fields of computational biology and bioinformatics. He has authored and coauthored some of the most groundbreaking tools to detect protein homology, study protein structure and evolution focusing on the use of statistical modeling. His work on the comparison of Hidden Markov Models and tools like HHblits, to detect remote homology in protein sequences, has significantly contributed to increase the scientific community's understanding of proteins in general. Also, the HHPred server has been one of the best performing servers in the last blind structure prediction CASP competitions during the last years. As an expert on improving the way in which to align protein sequences, he also collaborated on the development of Clustal Omega, which is one of the best performing softwares for aligning protein sequences. After more than a decade of successful work on the protein side of bioinformatics, Johannes Söding has expanded his research focus to many different research topics like single cell transcriptomics, transcriptional regulation, personalized medicine and others applying quantitative and edge-cutting statistical methodologies.

Sponsored Speakers

Fiona Nielsen, Founder and CEO, Repositive

Bioinformatics scientist specialised in genome analysis with 15 years of experience in software development and project management. Fiona left her job at Illumina Cambridge in 2013 to pursue her vision of enabling efficient genomic data sharing and founded the charity DNADigest. In August 2014 she founded Repositive as a spin out of DNADigest. Fiona will give a talk at SCS2017: *A bioinformaticians spark which lead to a new platform for sharing genomic data*

Thank You to Our Sponsors!

The ISCB Student Council Symposium depends on generous sponsorships from the following companies and organizations:

Session 1: Proteins, DNA, Sequences and Evolution

Determining the function of the apicomplexan 6-Cys/SRS protein family: a structural and evolutionary understanding of pathogen invasion

Eli Draizen, Beth Gregg, Patricia Sikorski, Gloria Adedoyin, Philippe Youkharibache, Dietlind L. Gerloff, Michael E. Grigg, Philip E. Bourne

Boston University, US

Background: Apicomplexan parasites have evolved specific repertoires of proteins to target and invade a variety of cells from a wide host range. The 6-Cys/SRS surface proteins are found in *Toxoplasma gondii* (the causative agent of Toxoplasmosis) and *Plasmodium spp.* (the causative agent of Malaria). The 6-Cys proteins are named after six conserved cysteine residues, which hold their beta-sandwich fold together through disulphide bridges. They are involved in adhesion and invasion at the host-pathogen interface, but the exact molecular details of the process remain unknown. To date, over 180 6-Cys domain-containing proteins have been identified in *Toxoplasma* but only 14 have been identified in *Plasmodium*, with only ~10% sequence similarity and shifted disulphide bonds. 6-Cys proteins are notoriously difficult to identify because they are divergent, have been lost due to pseudogenization, or have large loops between the last two beta strands.

Results: Using a structure-guided HMM, we discovered new 6-Cys family proteins throughout Apicomplexa. By aligning each domain hit and constructing a phylogenetic tree of the domains, we identified a single protein from *T. gondii* that had the shortest branch length to the *Plasmodium* proteins and a disulphide bond pattern similar to the disulphide pattern in *Plasmodium* 6-Cys, suggesting it may have retained a structure similar to its

ancestor. In order to assess its function, we knocked it out using CRISPR/Cas9, replacing it with a drug inducible gene cassette. We hypothesize that it plays a role in division and egress since the KO strains have been unable complete division or lyse host cells. We also identified new 6-Cys proteins in *Eimeria*, a basal Apicomplexan lineage.

Conclusion: We have identified a new 6-Cys protein in *T. gondii* that may resemble the ancestral fold and created a knock-out of it using CRISPR/Cas9. Understanding the evolution of the 6-Cys family will help us gain insights on host-pathogen interactions. 6-Cys proteins are likely exploiting molecular mimicry of host binding interfaces to evade immune system detection and drive invasion. We plan to model all 6-Cys proteins and identify new interaction partners from the immune system by electrostatic surface comparison and docking.

scTree: reconstructing complex cellular lineage trees from single-cell RNA-seq data

Rodrigo Gonzalo Parra, Nikolaos Papadopoulos, Laura Ahumada-Arranz, Jakob El Kolthei, Barbra Treutlein, Johannes Soeding

Max Planck Institute for Biophysical Chemistry, DE

Introduction: Recent advances in single-cell sequencing have facilitated to measure expression profiles for thousands of cells at once. Tissues often contain not only fully committed cells but also at intermediate stages. RNA-seq snapshots should allow us to reconstruct the complex cellular lineage trees that explain the emergence of differentiated cell fates from a single progenitor cell population, e.g. in embryonic development. The expression time courses along each edge of the lineage tree

could form the basis for dissecting the intricate gene interaction networks that regulate this process. Different techniques have shown to be successful in finding low-dimensional manifolds where cellular differentiation trees can be visualized. However, the problem of identification of correct lineage trees is not solved except for very simple topologies.

Results: We present **scTree**, a tool to reconstruct lineage trees from single-cell RNA-seq data. Once a manifold is calculated by some dimensionality reduction technique, end points, branch points, and their connectivity are detected, and cells are ordered according to a pseudotime measure along the branches of the tree. **scTree** calculates the denoised expression profile for each gene along each branch of the reconstructed lineage tree. By applying different statistical tests, genes that are differentially expressed among the different cell types that constitute the tree can be detected. While all state-of-the-art methods use a specific manifold space on which they reconstruct lineage tree structures, **scTree** is able to work in any given space, making it much more flexible. We were able to reconstruct tree lineage topologies for different datasets, both from real and simulated data, and compared the results with reconstructions made by other methods as well.

Conclusion: **scTree** can reconstruct complex tree topologies with multiple branching points robustly and accurately, surpassing the available methods in the field. Pseudotime courses for all genes on the tree are derived. The obtained high pseudotime resolution should enable the derivation of complex gene regulatory networks from snapshots of single-cell expression data. Tools like **scTree** will be of special importance in the immediate future as more and more complex differentiation processes are being investigated with single-cell RNA-seq techniques.

The impact of native state switching on protein sequence evolution

Avital Sharir-Ivry, Yu Xia

McGill University, CA

Background: For proteins with a single well-defined native state, protein 3D structure is a major determinant of sequence evolution. One of the strongest signals found is a linear relationship between residue evolutionary rate and residue burial or packing. On the other hand, many proteins adopt multiple, distinct native structures under different conditions (conformational switches), yet the impact of such native state switching on protein evolution is not fully understood.

Description: Here, we performed a proteome-wide analysis of how protein structure impacts sequence evolution for protein conformational switches in *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* using pooled analysis of sites with similar packing or burial. We observed a strong linear relationship between residue evolutionary rate and residue packing for conformational switches, similar to the observed trend for proteins with a single native state. In addition, we found that conformational switches evolve significantly and consistently more slowly than proteins with a single native state, even after controlling for degree of residue burial or packing. Next, we focused on proteins that switch conformations upon molecular binding. We found that interfacial residues in these conformational switches evolve more slowly than interfacial residues in proteins with a single native state, and that the bound conformation is a better predictor for residue evolutionary rate than the unbound conformation.

Conclusions: Our findings suggest that unlike flexible or disordered proteins, which are generally less constrained in sequence evolution, conformational switches evolve significantly more slowly than other proteins with a single native state. Moreover, for conformational switches, the necessity to encode multiple distinct native structures under different conditions imposes strong evolutionary constraints on the entire protein, rather than just a few key residues. Our results provide new insights into the structureevolution relationship

of protein conformational switches, and deeper understanding of the evolutionary design principles of protein conformational switches.

SequenceServer: a modern graphical user interface for BLAST

Anurag Priyam, Ben J. Woodcroft, Vivek Rai, Alekhya Munagala, Hiten Chowdhary, Ismail Moghul, Filip Ter, Mark Anthony Gibbins, HongKee Moon, Guy Leonard, Wolfgang Rumpf, Yannick Wurm
Queen Mary University of London, GB

The dramatic drop in DNA sequencing costs has created many opportunities for novel research that require comparing newly obtained and previously known sequences. This is commonly done with **BLAST**. However, running **BLAST** directly on new datasets and interpreting results requires substantial technical skills. Furthermore, graphical interfaces for **BLAST** are challenging to install and largely mimic underlying computational processes rather than work patterns of researchers.

We combined a user-centric design philosophy with sustainable software development ap-

proaches to create **SequenceServer**. The innovations in **SequenceServer** over other **BLAST** servers are at three levels. First, our software can be rapidly installed and used on custom datasets for individual use or sharing with a community. Second, by analysing user input and using simple algorithms, **SequenceServer** reduces the amount of decisions the user must make, provides interactive visual feedback, and prevents common potential errors that would otherwise cause erroneous results. Finally, **SequenceServer** provides multiple visual and text-based output options that mirror the requirements and work patterns of researchers.

The result of our approach has been successful as demonstrated by >35 mentions of the software in peer-reviewed publications, and shows how computational tools underlying basic scientific research can benefit from and appropriate consideration of user experience. Our software is particularly enabling for researchers and communities focusing on species for which genomic data is novel as it empowers them to independently and easily perform **BLAST** queries and share datasets.

Session 2: Networks and 3D Interactions

Differential network analysis hints at revealing mechanism of actions of combined drug applications

Mohamed Hamed, Sklarz L.-M, Gladbach Y.S, Ernst M, Roof C, Sender S, Sekora A, Beck J, Schtz E, Struckmann S, Junghan C, Fuellen G, Murua Escobar H
Rostock University Medical Center, DE

Background: Chemotherapeutic agents are one of the mainstays of anticancer treatments. Several agents are currently applied using different protocols and showing remarkable effectivity in the clinics. However, clinical effectivity is often accompanied by server side effects. Compound combination and investigation of application sequences could lead to novel therapeutic strategies in targeted therapy potentially enhancing effectiveness and or reducing side effects.

Description: We combined a PI3K-gamma inhibitor with the conventional chemotherapeutic agents cytarabine and dexamethasone on two B-ALL cell lines. We observed different drug response profiles between the two combination treatments in terms of various cell biological parameters such as cell proliferation, metabolic activities, late and early apoptosis. Accordingly, we performed whole transcriptome sequencing for each combination and utilized the differential network approach to dissect the induced effects and to understand the mechanisms of action of each combination therapy. Differential network analysis between the transcriptomes of the two combined treatments revealed the affected pathways and functional terms when applying the combined drugs. Moreover, we constructed the transcriptional networks in response to each combined treatment to get an informative picture of the dynamic changes in the associated gene regulatory network. We

further reduced each transcriptional network to a disease (Leukaemia)-specific network to contextualize drug effects towards Leukaemia and hence to better identify key players among the genes, TFs, and miRNAs.

Conclusion: Differential network approaches combined with gene regulatory analysis provide insights into mechanisms of action of drug application and they help to identify essential key players.

Reducing noise in Hi-C interaction matrices at restriction fragment resolution

Christopher JF Cameron, Jose Dostie and Mathieu Blanchette
McGill University, CA

Hi-C, the high-throughput derivative of chromosome conformation capture technology, allows for the quantification of all DNA-DNA contacts genome-wide found within a population of cells. The output of a Hi-C experiment is stored in an interaction frequency matrix. At the restriction fragment resolution, most Hi-C matrices are sparse due to the required depth and high costs associated with sequencing. A majority of pair-wise restriction-fragment interactions receive a raw frequency of zero or one, with most contacts found at relatively short distances (<1 megabase). Typically, interaction frequencies are analyzed at a fixed resolution (e.g., 50 kilobase) to increase their signal over noise ratio. The consequences of this reduction in resolution are that key interactions between fine-scale genomic elements (e.g., expression quantitative trait loci studies, enhancer/promoter interactions, chromatin looping events) may not be observed. A correct interpretation of Hi-C interaction frequency matrices relies on representing the observed data at the proper resolution, which involves a trade-off between signal and noise.

We describe two adaptive density estimation techniques that reduce noise by considering the changing density of restriction-fragment interactions across a Hi-C interaction frequency matrix while retaining the highest-possible resolution. The first is a novel application of a Markov random field to Hi-C data. To estimate true interaction frequency from Hi-C data, the random field considers both (i) the immediate neighborhood of restriction-fragment interactions and (ii) topologically associating domain boundaries. The second adaptive density estimation algorithm implements kernel density estimation with a dynamic bandwidth to consider surrounding restriction-fragment interactions.

We validate our adaptive density estimation algorithms by demonstrating that estimated matrices allow for higher accuracy in identifying true positive/negative contacts and provide a lower error when inferring interaction frequency across varying sequencing depths, compared to traditional fixed binning approaches. True positive interactions are Hi-C restriction-fragment interactions found to be mediated by RNA polymerase II and CTCF (as identified by ChIA-PET a chromosome conformation capture technology that incorporates chromatin immunoprecipitation). We also show that adaptive density estimated Hi-C interaction frequency matrices correlate better with 5C data (a targeted sequencing chromosome conformation capture technology with high sequencing depth) when observing the same genomic regions.

Intervene: a tool for intersection and visualization of multiple gene or genomic region sets

Aziz Khan, Anthony Mathelier

University of Oslo, NO

Background: A common task for scientists relies on comparing lists of genes or genomic regions derived from high-throughput sequencing experiments. While several tools exist to intersect and visualize sets of genes, similar tools dedicated to the visualization of genomic region sets are currently limited.

Results: To address this gap, we have developed the **Intervene** tool, which provides an easy and automated interface for the effective intersection and visualization of genomic region or list sets, thus facilitating their analysis and interpretation. **Intervene** contains three modules: `venn` to generate Venn diagrams of up to six sets, `upset` to generate UpSet plots of multiple sets, and `pairwise` to compute and visualize intersections of multiple sets as clustered heat maps. **Intervene**, and its interactive web ShinyApp companion, generate publication-quality figures for the interpretation of genomic region and list sets.

Conclusions: **Intervene** and its web application companion provide an easy command line, and an interactive web interface to compute intersections of multiple genomic and list sets. They also have the capacity to plot intersections using easy-to-interpret visual approaches. **Intervene** is developed and designed to meet the needs of both computer scientists and biologists. The source code is freely available at bitbucket.org/CBGR/intervene, with the web application available at asntech.shinyapps.io/intervene.

Modeling and Stochastic Simulation of Gene Regulatory Networks in *Escherichia coli*

Rodrigo Santibáñez, Daniel Garrido, Tomás Pérez-Acle, Alberto J.M. Martín

Fundacin Ciencia Vida, CL

Background: Our ability to develop modified and synthetic organisms tailored to biotechnology production is fostered by our ability to recombine DNA. However, our current capacities to understand how cells work are insufficient, challenging the modification and prediction of desired phenotypes. Interestingly, modeling allows cost-intensive manipulation of biological systems and computational resources could leverage experimental procedures. Traditionally, Ordinary Differential Equations (ODEs) have been employed, but it has been shown that cell processes are stochastic, discrete and structurally complex, hampering ODEs to fit these properties.

Description: To further resolve a connection between modeling and designing organisms, we present two Rule-Based Models (RBMs) resembling Gene Regulatory Networks (GRN) of *E. coli*. Rules are macroscopic chemical reactions between entities that recapitulate one or several patterns necessary for a transformation. Noteworthy, our laboratory has developed PISKaS, a simulation tool that enables explicit compartmentalized modeling and simulation. These models resemble the core network that regulates transcription and plasmid replication. The simulations were performed employing arbitrary rates, yet surprisingly, they predict properties in close agreement with experimental data. Specifically, when the core transcription network reached pseudo-equilibrium, it predicts free RNA Polymerase Holoenzyme close to 18%, relatively near the 28% reported for exponentially growing *E. coli*. Similarly, the plasmid replication predicts a saturation dynamic, producing tens or hundreds of copies depending strongly on the interaction rate between its non-coding RNAs.

Conclusion: We considered cells in a pseudo-stationary state, therefore disregarding the necessity to model other cell mechanisms. Although, metabolism and protein synthesis and degradation could be easily incorporated in successive refinements of our models. Importantly, linking metabolism to transcription and translation could facilitate a more reliable prediction of phenotype emergence. To this end, a GRN, a Genome-Scale Metabolic Model (GSMM) and a protein-protein and RNA-protein interaction networks will serve as inputs to draft RBMs automatically. We sought to model at genome-scale the Molecular Biology Central Dogma joint to metabolism. For instance, an RBM that resembles the published central metabolism of *E. coli* (MODEL1505110000) written employing the RegulonDB GRNs and the iJO1366 GSMM, resulted in comparable dynamics as the published model, making RBMs a plausible new paradigm modeling framework.

Discovery of murine tissue specific regulatory drivers and their impact

Siddharth Sethi, Simon Greenaway,
Kenneth Condon, John Williams, Michelle
Simon, Ann-Marie Mallon

MRC Harwell Institute, GB

Background: Tissue specific regulatory regions are important for various biomedical applications including manipulating gene expression in single cell types or tissues and for developing conditional mouse models. However, little is known about the relationship between specific regulatory regions and corresponding phenotypes of genes they control. Using an in silico integrated approach, we present a novel analysis to identify Tissue Specific Regulatory Elements (TSREs) that may directly or indirectly drive the genes that correspond with mutant mouse phenotypes.

Description: Using ChromHMM, a 6 state chromatin map was generated from 3 primary histone marks in 22 mouse tissues. We calculated the tissue specificity index (using Tau) of all strong enhancers and active promoters (posterior probability >0.95) across 22 epigenomes, and identified highly tissue specific regulatory elements (Tau >0.85). Using RNA-seq data we show that genes with strong/active TSREs have significantly higher expression compared to genes with weak or absent TSREs (p <0.0009 , permutation test). Interestingly, only $\sim 5\%$ of the tissue specific enhancers and $\sim 21\%$ of promoters identified in each epigenome are observed to drive tissue specific expression of their target genes. We integrated mammalian phenotype ontology terms with the putative target genes of TSREs and show significant correlation between mouse phenotypes and corresponding TSREs (enrichments $q < 2.87E-8$). Using a random forest model, we evaluated the capability of TSREs to predict mouse phenotypes and tissue specific active promoters achieved the greatest accuracy of $\sim 76\%$ (AUC=0.76) whilst enhancer and expression profiles achieved $\sim 67\%$ (AUC=0.77) and $\sim 67\%$ (AUC=0.80) respectively. To validate our predictions, we investigated protein-protein interactions (PPI) among TSRE genes in each epigenome and

observed significant interactions with corresponding phenotype associated partners (p-value=0). Simulating these PPI networks by adding random genes also showed that TSRE genes with novel gene-phenotype associations interact more with known phenotype genes compared to randomly added genes (p<0.02). Finally, we have identified known and novel transcription factors enriched in TSREs which

potentially play important regulatory roles in their corresponding epigenomes.

Conclusion: Overall, these data may identify tissue specific regulatory elements and novel gene-phenotype associations that can drive specific mouse phenotypes, and serves as a helpful resource for researchers to formulate new hypothesis about gene biological functions.

Session 3: Modeling Cancer, Viruses and Diseases

Logical modeling approaches as a proxy to analyze cardiovascular disease trajectories

Amel Bekkar, Julien Dorier, Isaac Crespo, Anne Niknejad, Cristina Casal, Anne Estreicher, Alan Bridge, Ioannis Xenarios
SIB, Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics, CH

Cardio-vascular diseases (CVDs) are the leading cause of mortality and morbidity in Europe and worldwide. They are complex, multifactorial, chronic and comorbidities pathologies that cannot be described or explained by reductionist view. In order to tackle this complex diseases we have developed a logical modeling framework that consists of three efforts. The first step is composed of an expert curation related to the body of literature that we called Prior Knowledge Network (PKN). The PKN is assembled from the existing knowledge and experimental evidence to include the relevant components for CVDs as well as the relationships between them (inhibition or activation). As compared to databases that register facts and summarize them, we have encoded the logical rules of regulations, enabling the use of the PKN for modeling and simulation. The second step simulate the cellular decision process and identify the phenotype attained by the regulatory networks. As the PKN is large (729 node, 3406 logical rules) a manual optimization would be time consuming and its simulation computationally demanding which requires the use of approaches such as `Optimusqual`, an optimization method that uses a genetic algorithm to find in the PKN the sub-graph that reproduces as well as possible a training set built from experimental data such as gene expression data. In the final step we simulate several in silico perturbations either known or unknown in the field of CVD. That allows us in one hand to evaluate and assess the

pertinence of our model and in the other hand to make predictions and generate new testable hypotheses about driver nodes able to switch the network phenotype.

Fidelity of contig spectra based community modelling for estimating viral diversity measures using metaviromes

Damayanthi Herath, Dr. Sen-Lin Tang, Dr. David Ackland, Prof. Saman K. Halgamuge
The University of Melbourne, The University of Peradeniya, AU, LK

Background: Metagenomics has enabled the study of viruses without the need for culturing their hosts in a laboratory or the availability of phylogenetic marker genes to distinguish them. Species richness and evenness are two widely used species diversity measures. A plot of relative abundance against abundance rank, i.e. the rank-abundance curve may be used to visualise the community structure. The state-of-the-art method for estimating viral diversity measures from a metavirome—a metagenome of viruses employs the contig spectrum. The common approach for estimating viral diversity is to model the expected contig spectrum and estimate the corresponding diversity measures giving the smallest difference between predicted and observed contig spectra.

Description: In this study, we explored the fidelity of the existing contig spectrum based modelling approach for evaluating various viral communities using iterative simulation. Four viral-population-specific parameters were considered, including the evenness, viral richness, average genome size and rank-abundance curve form. The variation of differences between two contig spectra generated

from the existing model over the considered parameters was explored and represented by a distance matrix. The distance matrix representation can then be used to identify viral communities for which contig spectrum analysis may then be applied. Using this distance matrix, it was identified that existing model for contig spectrum can be used to uniquely capture communities with a rank-abundance curve of the form of lognormal or logarithmic. However, it cannot generate unique contig spectra for a set of communities with certain combinations of average genome size and evenness values and a power law or an exponential rank-abundance curve form.

Conclusions: In this study, an existing model for generating contig spectra which may be used to estimate viral diversity measures was evaluated for its ability to capture different viral communities uniquely. This study identified properties of viral communities for which the aforementioned model cannot generate unique contig spectra. The results of this study provide insights for further analysis of viral diversity measures estimated based on contig spectrum and benchmarking methods for estimating viral diversity.

Integrating diverse transcriptomic alterations to identify cancer-relevant genes and signatures

Natalie Davidson, PanCancer Analysis of Whole Genomes and Transcriptomes Working Group (PCAWG-3), PCAWG Consortium, Kjong-Van Lehmann, Andr Kahles, Alvis Brazma, Angela N. Brooks, Claudia Calabrese, Nuno A. Fonseca, Jonathan Goke, Roland F Schwarz, Gunnar Rtsch, Zemin Zhang

ETH Zurich, CH

Background: We present a novel analysis that 1) identifies cancer driver genes through a recurrence analysis over diverse types of transcriptomic alterations 2) identifies frequent and heterogeneous transcriptomic alteration signatures in 1190 samples across 25 cancer types as part of the Pan-Cancer Analysis of Whole Genomes (PCAWG)

of the International Cancer Genome Consortium (ICGC). We integrated the following alteration types: expression outliers, alternative splicing outliers, gene fusions, alternative promoters, somatic variants, RNA-editing, and allele-specific expression.

Results: To identify the cancer relevant genes, we created a new method for performing recurrence analysis on transcriptomic features. Our method has three main strengths: flexibility to handle any number or type of alteration, sensitivity to different frequencies of alterations, and ability to prioritize genes with heterogeneous alterations. To ensure statistical significance did >1M permutations to identify a cut-off for informative scores; our analysis yielded 338 genes with passing scores. These genes show a 3.47-fold enrichment for cancer census genes and driver genes (from PCAWG-9) with an FDR corrected p-value of 3.15e-21, signifying that our analysis is identifying cancer-relevant genes. In addition to our recurrence analysis, we characterize cancer-types and individual samples by their transcriptomic alteration patterns and connect them to DNA-level aberrations. Through our comparison of alteration frequencies we notice that alteration patterns greatly vary between the cancer types (SKCM/KIRC), but similar cancers tend to have similar alteration patterns (KIRC/KIRP). To tie RNA-patterns to DNA-level aberrations, we correlated the patterns with mutational signatures (MSig), provided by PCAWG-7. For visualization, we restricted ourselves to dominating MSigs 4, 7a, and 40. We find that signature 40 seems to be described by a higher amount of alternative promoter usage, expression outliers, and splicing; and fewer somatic variants, RNA editing, allele-specific expression, and fusions.

Conclusions: Through our joint analysis, we were able to integrate both DNA/RNA aberrations into a recurrence analysis that yielded a list of promising genes highly enriched for known cancer driver genes. Furthermore, we were able to correlate the various types of transcriptomic alterations to cancer type and DNA-level aberrations, helping to broadly explain the influence of the transcriptome on various cancer processes.

A comprehensive meta-analysis of the induced immediate early response reveals a conserved order of promoter activation

Annalaura Vacca, Stuart Aitken, Colin A Semple

Edinburgh University, GB

Background: Human cells respond to a broad range of stimuli with a characteristic burst of transcription within minutes at many sites across the genome; this underlies differentiation, responses to cellular stress, and inflammation. The earliest events involve the transient activation of the promoters of immediate-early genes (IEGs), a special class of genes dysregulated in developmental diseases and cancer. However, the core IEG repertoire active across cellular responses, and the mechanisms underlying IEG induction remain controversial.

Description: Here we present a rigorous meta-analysis of 8 genome-wide FANTOM5 CAGE time course expression datasets. These unique datasets measure the responses of different human cell types (including embryonic, immune and cancer cells) to many different stimuli over the first 5 hours post stimulus. Using novel approaches we classify promoter expression profiles to several predefined patterns, including a transient early peak representing IEG dynamics, to identify the likely core complement of IEGs. These genes are strongly enriched for known IEGs and relevant Gene Ontology terms, but also include a number of compelling novel IEG candidates, including transcription factors and noncoding RNAs. However, comparing genes classified as IEGs between datasets we found differences in their numbers and identity, which explain the heterogeneity and inconsistencies of the literature related to the immediate-early response. Furthermore, we show that the promoters of many candidate and known IEGs are activated in a consistent order across datasets, suggesting deeper levels of conservation in the regulation of immediate-early responses.

Conclusions: Here we exploit unusual, densely sampled promoter expression datasets using novel approaches to estimate the core

IEG response of human cells to cellular stimuli. We discuss surprising candidate IEGs that may be important new factors in diseases related processes and the potential roles for non-coding RNAs in the immediate-early response. We also uncover unexpected conservation in the temporal order of promoter activation across stimuli and cell types.

Predicting abnormal circadian phenotypes in mouse

John Williams, Siddharth Sethi, Patrick Nolan, Michelle Simon, Georgios Gkoutos, Ann-Marie Mallon

MRC Harwell Institute, GB

Background: Disruptions in circadian rhythms have been associated with disorders ranging from schizophrenia to bipolar disorder, implicating mutations in known circadian clock genes as potential therapeutic targets or biomarkers of mental illness. In mouse models, gene function can be discovered by reverse genetic screens by analyzing phenotypes of knockout or mutagenized mouse lines. Current large phenotype programs such as the International Mouse Phenotype Consortium test for a variety of behavioral phenotypes, but circadian related assays are not widespread. To prioritize candidates for circadian phenotype screens, we used machine learning approaches to predict the abnormal circadian rhythm phenotype in mouse genes.

Description: We analyzed RNA-Sequencing libraries from two mouse tissues: the central pacemaker clock of the suprachiasmatic nucleus, and a peripheral clock tissue liver. We detected signature circadian oscillations in each tissues expression, indicative of circadian characteristics. Abundance of expression in the central clock and relative expression distributions throughout 26 tissues were also shown to be indicative of potential circadian phenotype. Using protein-protein interaction graphs, we constructed a diffusion kernel on known interactions, scoring nodes from short random walks around known circadian genes. These were used as features in a RUSBoost ensemble tree classifier. 91 genes with annotated abnormal circadian rhythm

phenotypes were used as positive targets. A total of 275 out of 12502 protein coding genes expressed in the suprachiasmatic nucleus were predicted to have novel abnormal phenotypes. Highly ranked are known clock genes have no abnormal circadian mouse phenotypes in mouse, but present circadian phenotypes in human orthologs. Known circadian genes *Npas2* and *Fbxw11* were successfully predicted to contribute to circadian phenotypes.

Conclusions: Machine learning predicts genes which, if disturbed, may contribute to abnormal circadian phenotypes in mouse. Potential novel circadian functions will require experimental validation. Our findings highlight bias in mammalian phenotype annotations, reflecting both what has been studied to date in mouse, and the redundancy in the mammalian clock. Inferring mammalian phenotypes has potential to improve whole-phenome approaches to disease prioritization in humans. Using a combination gene expression and protein graph metrics, our machine learning method reduces the search space for phenotype annotations.

TOPSPIN: a novel algorithm to predict treatment specific survival in cancer

Joske Ubels, Erik H. van Beers, Pieter Sonneveld, Martin H. van Vliet, Jeroen de Ridder

UMC Utrecht, NL

Background: Cancer treatment can have heterogeneous response rates, while they are often associated with serious side effects. Treatment response may well be improved by selecting the right treatment for the right patient at the moment of diagnosis. This requires the discovery of predictive markers, i.e. markers that are able to predict whether a patient will benefit from treatment. The discovery of markers like these, for example gene expression signatures, remains a major challenge. Here we propose TOPSPIN (Treatment Outcome Prediction using Similarity between PatIeNts), a new computational method to discover gene expression signatures capable of identifying a subgroup of patients more likely to benefit from a specific treatment as compared to another

treatment. TOPSPIN relies on the idea that potential signature gene sets can be identified by searching for patients with similar gene expression profiles, who exhibit large survival differences when receiving a different treatment.

Description: TOPSPIN aims to predict whether a patient will benefit (class 1) or will not benefit (class 0) from a certain treatment of interest based on the gene expression profile of the patient. We demonstrate its utility in a multiple myeloma dataset, where patients either received the proteasome inhibitor bortezomib or some other treatment. We identify 8 Gene Ontology gene sets that can be used to identify a subset of patients that benefit significantly more from bortezomib than the population as a whole. In an independent validation set ($n = 304$) we identify a class 1, comprising 27.0% of patients, that has a more than two-fold benefit when receiving bortezomib (Hazard Ratio = 0.47, $p = 0.03$). In contrast, the patients in class 0 see no benefit from bortezomib (Hazard Ratio = 0.93, $p = 0.73$).

Conclusion: We demonstrate that TOPSPIN is capable of finding a classifier that can predict treatment specific survival and validates in independent data. TOPSPIN can be applied to any dataset with a continuous outcome measure and two treatment arms. For cancer drugs associated with low response rates it can help identify patients that will benefit and prevent ineffective treatment for other patients.

Homology modeling in a dynamical world

Alexander Monzon, Diego Javier Zea, Cristina Marino-Buslje, Gustavo Parisi

Universidad Nacional de Quilmes, AR

Background: Template-based modeling (TBM) is nowadays the most reliable approach for protein structure prediction. A key concept in TBM is the high correlation between sequence and structural divergence, which practical consequence is that homologous proteins similar at the sequence level will be also similar at the structural level. TBM success will be proportional to target and template sequence similarity. However, the native state

of proteins is composed of conformers in a dynamical equilibrium. Under this view, a single sequence will exist in several conformations showing different levels of structural differences which define its conformational diversity (CD). Considering the CD will then blurs the correlation between structural and sequence divergence due to substitutions occurred during evolution, just because structural variation is present without sequence changes.

Description: In this work we explore the impact that conformational diversity could have in the relationship between structural and sequence divergence. To this end, we analysed a curated data set composed of 2024 proteins with known experimental CD, clustered in 524 homologous families (>30% local identity and 90% coverage) used to derive structural and sequence similarities.

Conclusions: We have found that the extent of CD can be as high as the maximum structural divergence among the families and in this sense can not be neglected. Also, as expected, CD impairs the well established correlation between sequence and structure divergence which becomes more noisy than the previously studied. However, we found that this noise could be resolved using a priori information coming from structure-function relationship. We showed that protein families with low CD, show a well correlated behaviour of sequence and structure divergence, which is severely reduced in proteins with larger CD. This lack of correlation could impair TBM results in highly dynamical proteins. Finally, we also found that the presence of order/disorder could be a useful beforehand information for a better TBM performance.

Influence of temperature in the conformational change of Zika Virus E protein and its consequences in viral infectivity

Gabriela Muniz, Rafael Souza, Andrei Siqueira, Evonildo Goncalves, Joo Vianez.
Evandro Chagas Institute , BR

Zika Virus (ZIKV) is a flavivirus transmitted mainly by mosquitoes of the genus *Aedes*. Its envelope (E) protein is responsible for the

entry of flaviviruses into the cell and has three domains (DI, DII and DIII), where the DII domain has a fusion loop at its distal tip. The E protein of Dengue Virus 2, another Flavivirus, exhibits high structural similarity to the Zika virus E protein, and undergoes a temperature dependent conformational change that drives the shape of the viral particle from a smooth to bumpy (more infective) shape. This change increases infection in mammalian cells, exposing areas of the viral membrane that are essential for the fusion with host cells. For this reason, we analysed how temperature can influence the conformation of protein E of the Zika virus, aiming to describe large-scale collective movements that may have a major impact on the transition from the smooth to the bumpy form and consequently drive viral infectivity. Two different temperatures were simulated using accelerated molecular dynamics technique: 4 and 27, for a total of 100ns for each system. Principal component analyses (PCA) determined biologically relevant and different preferred conformations at the studied temperatures when using the two most important PCs. The higher amplitude movements found by PCA analysis demonstrated the approximation of the two domains of the protein through flexion mediated by the hinge region located between the domains III and II of the protein E. According to the free energy landscape analyses, when the system was simulated at 4 the preferred conformation was very similar to the smooth (less infectious) form of DENV-2. On the other hand, at 27 the preferred conformation was more similar to the bumpy (more infectious) form of DENV-2. We could also infer that the change from smooth to bumpy form is associated with the transition of a region in the DII from a loop to β -strand conformation at 27.

Mining CD8+ T-cell receptor patterns underlying immunogenic peptide recognition

Nicolas De Neuter, Wout Bittremieux, Charlie Beirnaert, Bart Cuypers, Aida Mrzic, Pieter Moris, Viggo Van Tendeloo, Arvid Suls, Benson Ogunjimi, Kris Laukens, Pieter Meysman

University of Antwerp, BE

Current T-cell epitope prediction tools are a valuable resource in designing targeted immunogenicity experiments. They typically focus on, and are able to, accurately predict peptide binding and presentation by MHC molecules on the surface of antigen-presenting cells. However, recognition of the peptide-MHC complex by a T-cell receptor is often not included in these tools. In this work we show the feasibility of extending epitope prediction models, which typically only include peptide preprocessing and/or major histocompatibility complex binding steps, to models that incorporate T-cell receptor binding information.

In this work, we show that predicting whether a peptide is recognized by a given T-cell receptor is a feasible task. In first instance, we showed this by training a random forest classifier to assign which of two HIV-1 derived, B*08-restricted peptides is bound by a given T-cell receptor, based on experimental data obtained from the literature. These results suggest that T-cell receptor sequence data contains sufficient information to infer peptide recognition. To further consolidate these results, we trained a separate classifier for each of the above peptides capable of retrieving T-cell receptors that bind the given peptide from a large set of irrelevant T-cell receptors. Furthermore, due to the non-black-box nature of random forest classifiers and the use of easily interpretable, biologically relevant features, these models are able to hint towards structurally important features of the T-cell receptors peptide-binding CDR3 region.

These results are of particularly importance as they show that prediction of T-cell epitope and T-cell epitope recognition based on sequence data is a feasible approach. In addition, the validity of our models not only

serves as a proof of concept for the prediction of immunogenic T-cell epitopes but also paves the way for more general and high performing models. This presents a significant step forward in the computational analysis of peptide immunogenicity, which is crucial to rational vaccine design as well as understanding complex immunological research areas such as auto-immunity and tumor susceptibility.

CRISPyS: gene family silencing using the CRISPR-Cas9 system

Gal Hyams, Shiran Abadi, Adi Avni, Eilon Shani, Eran Halperin, Itay Mayrose

Tel Aviv University, IL

The CRISPR-Cas9 system forms a bacterial immune system that recently has been adopted as a genome-editing technique of eukaryote genomes. The system is directed to the genomic site using a programmed single-guide RNA (sgRNA) that base-pairs with the DNA target, subsequently leading to a site-specific double-strand break. The binding affinity of the CRISPR-Cas9 system does not require perfect matching between the sgRNA and the DNA target. Thus, in addition to cleaving the desired on-target, cleavage may occur at multiple unintended genomic sites (termed off-targets) that are similar, up to a certain degree, to the on-target. Due to extensive history of local and large-scale genome duplications, many eukaryotic genomes harbor many large gene families of partially overlapping functions. This redundancy often results in a buffering effect: most single null mutants present no or minimal phenotypic consequence due to the overlapping function of one or more paralogs. Therefore, in many cases, the silencing of multiple family members of a gene family is necessary to uncover any phenotypic effects. Here, we introduce graph-based algorithms for the optimal design of potential sgRNA. The developed algorithms harness the low specificity of the CRISPR-Cas9 system to target multiple members of a given gene family. In-silico examination over all gene families in the *Solanum lycopersicum* genome shows that our suggested approach outperforms simpler alignment-based techniques. The utility

of the developed algorithm is further demonstrated in vivo by successfully silencing an entire family of gibberellin transporters in *S. lycopersicum* consisting of seven members using a single sgRNA.

Global proteomics profiling improves drug sensitivity prediction: results from a multi-omics, pan-cancer modeling approach

Mehreen Ali, Suleiman A. Khan, Krister Wennerberg, Tero Aittokallio

Institute for Molecular Medicine, University of Helsinki, FI

Background: Proteomics profiling is increasingly being used for molecular stratification of cancer patients and cell-line panels. However, systematic assessment of the predictive power of large-scale proteomic technologies for various drug classes and cancer types is currently lacking. To that end, we carried out the first pan-cancer, multi-omics comparative analysis of the relative performance of two proteomic technologies, targeted reverse phase protein array (RPPA) and global mass spectrometry (MS), in terms of their accuracy for predicting the sensitivity of cancer cells to both cytotoxic chemotherapeutics and molecularly-targeted anticancer compounds.

Description: Our results in two cell-line panels demonstrate how MS profiling improves drug response predictions beyond that of the RPPA or the other omics profiles alone. However, frequent missing MS data values complicate its use in predictive modeling and required filtering, such as focusing on completely-measured or known oncoproteins, to obtain maximal predictive performance. Rather strikingly, the two proteomic profiles provided complementary predictive signal both for the cytotoxic and targeted compounds. Further, information about the cellular-abundance of primary target proteins was found critical for predicting the response of targeted compounds, although the non-target features also contributed significantly to the predictive power.

Conclusion: Global MS data are more informative for drug response prediction as com-

pared to targeted RPPA technology. Furthermore, the clinical relevance of the selected protein markers was confirmed in cancer patient data. These results provide novel insights into the relative performance and optimal use of the widely-applied proteomic technologies, MS and RPPA, which should prove useful in translational applications, such as defining the best combination of omics technologies and markers for understanding and predicting drug sensitivities in cancer patients.

Computational proteogenomic identification of translated fusions and micro structural variations in cancer

Yen-Yi Lin, Alex Gawronski, Faraz Hach, Sujun Li, Ibrahim Numanagic, Iman Sarrafi, Swati Mishra, Andrew McPherson, Colin Collins Milan Radovich, Haixu Tang, S. Cen Sahinalp

Simon Fraser University, CA

Rapid advancement in high throughput sequencing (HTS) and mass spectrometry (MS) technologies has enabled the acquisition of the genomic, transcriptomic and proteomic data from the same tissue sample. Notably, The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA) and Clinical Proteomic Tumor Analysis Consortium (CPTAC) provide proteogenomics characterization of colonrectal and breast cancer patients, but they focus primarily on single amino acid variants and novel isoforms. Genomic aberrations that are frequently observed in specific cancer types, such as fusions, inversions, and duplications, are not included in existing proteogenomics studies. Once they occur in coding regions, however, these aberrations can generate novel proteins with highest impact on cancer phenotypes and are more likely to cause disease.

We introduce a computational framework which can integratively analyze all three types of omics data to obtain a complete molecular profile, especially translated fusions and micro structural variants, of a tissue sample. Our framework includes **MiStrVar**, an algorithmic method to identify micro structural variants (microSVs) on genomic HTS data. Coupled with the popular fusion detection tool

deFuse, our framework first provides an accurate profile of structurally aberrant transcripts in cancer samples. Given the obtained breakpoints, we use ProTIE in the framework to identify all relevant peptides spanning the breakpoint junctions, and match them with unique proteomic signatures in the respective proteomics data sets. We have applied our framework to 105 TCGA breast cancer patients with NGS data for which proteomics data from CPTAC have been released, and we detected 244 novel peptides from 432 candidate genomic/transcriptomic aberrations. Many of the aberrations we discovered have not been reported before, and the most significantly enriched genes involved in these translated aberrations are cancer-related or tumor suppressor genes. Interestingly, the vast majority of these translated aberrations were private, demonstrating the extensive inter-genomic heterogeneity present in breast cancer.

To conclude, our frameworks ability to observe structural aberrations at three levels of omics data provides a means of validating their presence. It can help researchers to obtain a comprehensive molecular profiling of cancer patients, which is important in various fields including immunogenomics and personalized medicine.

Zippering and assembly with limited sets of constraints

Maryana Wanggren, Martin Billeter,
Graham J.L. Kemp

Chalmers University of Technology, SE

NMR experiments provide a variety of restraints that can be used when constructing a model structure. Some experiments are relatively straightforward and are routinely performed when studying a new protein. Residual dipolar couplings (RDCs) are the easiest data to obtain for large proteins and give restraints related to torsion angles and also to the orientation (in a fixed coordinate system) of selected bonds, often the N-H bonds of the backbone. Other experiments require alternative isotope labelling or multidimensional NMR, which make the experiments very time-consuming and more expensive. One is often

faced with limited and sometimes insufficient information for determining a well-resolved 3D structure. In addition, the type of data available for different proteins may vary: ranges for torsion angles, distance approximations, relative orientation of different molecular parts etc. We want to build accurate model structures quickly (a few minutes), using only data that are easy to obtain.

A protein modelling program has been implemented that uses the zippering and assembly method in which longer fragments are constructed from pairs of shorter ones. The built fragments must be free from steric clashes, and be compatible with given constraints. Distance constraints can be propagated: new constraints lower in the zippering and assembly data structure can guide the conformational search towards feasible solutions. We are currently testing our method with a range of proteins by generating ensembles of structures based on only secondary structure information and disulphide bridges. The resulting models are compared with experimentally determined structures from the Protein Data Bank.

Computational methods for detection of allele specific expression and their diagnostic relevance for rare Mendelian disorders

Numrah Fadra, Eric Klee, Gavin Oliver

University of Minnesota, Mayo Clinic , US

Background: In recent years, development of bioinformatics methods for integration of genome and transcriptome datasets has become a widespread approach for detection of allelic imbalance in rare genetic syndromes. Allele specific expression is governed by novel and/or inherited genetic mutations within regulatory regions of the genome. However, detection of allelic imbalance is a major challenge due to technical and biological variation in the data and absence of standard normal datasets. One of the aspects of this study involves thorough evaluation and understanding of currently published methods for detection of biological events such as loss of heterozygosity and genetic imprinting. The analysis would help us understand the drawbacks of existing

statistical approaches and build a robust computational framework for accurate diagnoses of rare Mendelian disorders.

Description: The study makes use of whole genome and transcriptome sequencing datasets for patients displaying clinical phenotypes of rare genetic diseases. We generated a profile for heterozygous mutations from whole genome data. In the next step, we studied the distribution of these loci within the transcriptome data in terms of reference and alternate allele frequency and sequencing depth. Using these features as a guide, we designed an algorithm for identification of allelic imbalance at the gene level and validated the presence of several genetically imprinted transcripts. This is a crucial step as we try to understand the mechanism of loss of heterozygosity. Further, our aim is to evaluate existing methods for

building an improved, more accurate model to help us better understand the role of genome function and its effect on allele imbalance.

Conclusions: Several rare genetic diseases and traits can be explained by allele specific expression. Recent studies have demonstrated that allelic bias can be inferred per gene using statistical approaches such as a T-test, fishers exact test and beta binomial models; however, each method has its own limitations. We thoroughly reviewed existing methods and developed an algorithm to characterize the mutation profiles for genes showing strongly skewed monoallelic expression. The application of such complex bioinformatics algorithms for building an accurate computational framework has invaluable diagnostic relevance in the field of personalized and precision medicine.

Poster Presentations

1 The CD4+ T cell regulatory network mediates inflammatory responses during acute hyperinsulinemia: a simulation study

Mariana Esther Martinez-Sanchez, Marcia Hiriart, Elena Alvarez-Buylla
Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, MX

2 HPC pipeline for metagenomics

Trust Odia
Covenant University Bioinformatics Research G, NG

3 Darkness and disorder: an insight on the unknown portion of proteomes

Nicola Bordin, Julian Heinrich, Zsuzsanna Dosztanyi, Damien Devos, Sen I. ODonoghue
Universidad Pablo de Olavide, ES

4 Pan-cancer classification of gene signatures for their information value and functional redundancy

Laura Cantini, Laurence Calzone, Emmanuel Barillot, Loredana Martignetti, Andrei Zinovyev
Institut Curie, INSERM U900, PSL Research Uni, FR

5 Discovery of novel hits against *Leishmania* spp. crystallized proteins through a structure-based methodology using grid computing

Rodrigo Ochoa, Stanley J. Watowich, Andrs Flrez, Sara M. Robledo, Carlos Muskus
Max Planck Tandem Group, Biophysics of Tropic, CO

6 A comprehensive meta-analysis of the induced immediate early response reveals a conserved order of promoter activation

Annalaura Vacca, Stuart Aitken, Colin A Semple
Edinburgh University, GB

7 Zipping and assembly with limited sets of constraints

Maryana Wanggren, Martin Billeter, Graham J.L. Kemp
Chalmers University of Technology, SE

8 Logical modeling approaches as a proxy to analyze cardiovascular disease trajectories

Amel Bekkar, Julien Dorier, Isaac Crespo, Anne Niknejad, Cristina Casal, Anne Estreicher, Alan Bridge, Ioannis Xenarios
SIB, Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics, CH

9 Prediction of HIV-1 sensitivity to broadly neutralizing antibodies shows a trend towards resistance over time

Anna Hake, Nico Pfeifer
Max Planck Institute for Informatics, DE

10 Predicting abnormal circadian phenotypes in mouse

John Williams, Siddharth Sethi, Patrick Nolan, Michelle Simon, Georgios Gkoutos, Ann-Marie Mallon
MRC Harwell Institute, GB

- 11** Discovery of murine tissue specific regulatory drivers and their impact
Siddharth Sethi, Simon Greenaway, Kenneth Condon, John Williams, Michelle Simon, Ann-Marie Mallon
MRC Harwell Institute, GB
- 12** Fidelity of contig spectra based community modelling for estimating viral diversity measures using metaviromes
Damayanthi Herath, Dr. Sen-Lin Tang, Dr. David Ackland, Prof. Saman K. Halgamuge
The University of Melbourne, The University of Peradeniya, AU, LK
- 13** Differential network analysis hints at revealing mechanism of actions of combined drug applications
Mohamed Hamed, Sklarz L.-M, Gladbach Y.S, Ernst M, Roolf C, Sender S, Sekora A, Beck J, Schtz E, Struckmann S, Junghan C, Fuellen G, Murua Escobar H
Rostock University Medical Center, DE
- 14** Reducing noise in Hi-C interaction matrices at restriction fragment resolution
Christopher JF Cameron, Jose Dostie and Mathieu Blanchette
McGill University, CA
- 15** High-throughput Protein Functional Prediction by Data Science Approach
Yi-Wei Liu, Wen-Hung Liao, Jia-Ming Chang
National Chengchi University, Taiwan, TW
- 16** Lineage tree topology reconstruction for early myeloid progenitor cells
Jakob El Kholtei, Johannes Soeding, R. Gonzalo Parra
Max Planck Institute for Biophysical Chemistr, DE
- 17** **Intervene**: a tool for intersection and visualization of multiple gene or genomic region sets
Aziz Khan, Anthony Mathelier
University of Oslo, NO
- 18** **TOPSPIN**: a novel algorithm to predict treatment specific survival in cancer
Joske Ubels, Erik H. van Beers, Pieter Sonneveld, Martin H. van Vliet, Jeroen de Ridder
UMC Utrecht, NL
- 19** An evolutionary perspective on Chemokine Receptor Family
Tarun Jairaj Narwani, Sophie Abby, Alexandre G. de Brevern
INSERM, U 1134, DSIMB, Univ Paris Diderot, So, FR
- 20** An efficient contamination removal tool for improving prokaryotic genome assembly
Diya Sen, Mathu Malar Chandrababunaidu, Sucheta Tripathy
CSIR Indian Institute of Chemical Biology, IN
- 21** Development of Randomization-based enrichment analysis system
Mikhail Grishchenko, Alexander Yakimenko, Anastasiia Lazareva, Marat Khairetdinov
Institute of Computational Mathematics and Ma, RU
- 22** High-throughput identification of novel intrinsically disordered proteins in *Arabidopsis thaliana* during abiotic stress
Ingrid Tomljanovic, Karlo Skube, Dubravko Pavokovic
University of Zagreb, HR
- 23** Characterization and Evolutionary study of Chemosensory receptors in Basal-Hymenoptera
George F. Obiero, Bill S. Hansson, Ewald Grosse-Wilde
Max Planck Institute for Chemical Ecology, DE

24 Comparative integrated-omic analyses of phage-host interactions within natural and engineered microbial communities

Susana Martnez Arbas, Shaman Narayanasamy, Malte Herold, Emilie Muller, Patrick May, Paul Wilmes
University of Luxembourg, LU

25 Homology modeling in a dynamical world

Alexander Monzon, Diego Javier Zea, Cristina Marino-Buslje, Gustavo Parisi
Universidad Nacional de Quilmes, AR

26 Construction and analysis of a comprehensive protein interaction network of HCV with its host *Homo sapiens*

QuratulAin Farooq, Faisal F. Khan
Institute of Integrative Biosciences, CECOS U, PK

27 A novel primer design approach for the amplification of B cell cDNA encoding broadly neutralizing antibodies against human immunodeficiency virus

Matthias Dring, Christoph Kreer, Nathalie Lehnen, Nico Pfeifer, Florian Klein
Max Planck Institute for Informatics, DE

28 Structural Comparison of RNA using Boolean Logic

Diren Senger, Jannes Hke, Rdiger Ehlers
University of Bremen, DE

29 PopCluster: A New Algorithm to Identify Genetic Variants with Effects that Change with Ethnicity

Anastasia Gurinovich, John Farrell, Harold Bae, Annibale Puca, Gil Atzmon, Nir Barzilai, Thomas Perls, Paola Sebastiani

Boston University, US

30 Protein features mapped to the human genome

David Stanek, David Stanek, Dana Bis, Cima Saghira, Adriana Rebelo, Alex J. Abrams, Pavel Seeman, Petra Lassuthova, Stephan Zuchner

Department of Pediatric Neurology, DNA Lab, CZ

31 SequenceServer: a modern graphical user interface for BLAST

Anurag Priyam, Ben J. Woodcroft, Vivek Rai, Alekhya Munagala, Hiten Chowdhary, Ismail Moghul, Filip Ter, Mark Anthony Gibbins, HongKee Moon, Guy Leonard, Wolfgang Rumpf, Yannick Wurm

Queen Mary University of London, GB

32 Influence of temperature in the conformational change of Zika Virus E protein and its consequences in viral infectivity

Gabriela Muniz, Gabriela Muniz, Rafael Souza, Andrei Siqueira, Evonildo Goncalves, Joo Vianez.

Evandro Chagas Institute , BR

33 Determining the function of the apicomplexan 6-Cys/SRS protein family: a structural and evolutionary understanding of pathogen invasion

Eli Draizen, Beth Gregg, Patricia Sikorski, Gloria Adedoyin, Philippe Youkharibache, Dietlind L. Gerloff, Michael E. Grigg, Philip E. Bourne

Boston University, US

34 Data analysis to improve understanding and prediction of cross-resistance and epistatic interactions

Alexander Flohr, Prof. Dr. Volkhard Helms, Daria Gaidar

Saarland University, DE

35 Integrating diverse transcriptomic alterations to identify cancer-relevant genes and signatures

Natalie Davidson, PanCancer Analysis of Whole Genomes and Transcriptomes Working Group (PCAWG-3), PCAWG Consortium, Kjong-Van Lehmann, Andr Kahles, Alvis Brazma, Angela N. Brooks, Claudia Calabrese, Nuno A. Fonseca, Jonathan Goke, Roland F Schwarz, Gunnar Rtsch, Zemin Zhang

ETH Zurich, CH

36 Percolation-like phase transitions in protein-protein interaction networks of fusions reveal a discrepancy in cancer phenotypes

Somnath Tagore, Milana Frenkel-Morgenstern

BAR-ILAN UNIVERSITY, IL

37 Mining CD8+ T-cell receptor patterns underlying immunogenic peptide recognition

Nicolas De Neuter, Wout Bittremieux, Charlie Beirnaert, Bart Cuypers, Aida Mrzic, Pieter Moris, Viggo Van Tendeloo, Arvid Suls, Benson Ogunjimi, Kris Laukens, Pieter Meysman

University of Antwerp, BE

38 SwissProtSelect: The New Protein Superfamily Database Implemented by HMMERCTTER for Reliable Function Assignment

Nicolas Stocchi, Agustin Amalfitano, Marcel Brun, Arjen ten Have

IIB-CONICET-UNMdP, AR

39 Identifying Novel Peroxisomal Proteins by Multiple Kernel and One-Class Semi-Supervised Learning

Amir Abbas Zounemat Kermani

Imperial College London, GB

40 CRISPyS: gene family silencing using the CRISPR-Cas9 system

Gal Hyams, Shiran Abadi, Adi Avni, Eilon Shani, Eran Halperin, Itay Mayrose

Tel Aviv University, IL

41 scTree: reconstructing complex cellular lineage trees from single-cell RNA-seq data

Rodrigo Gonzalo Parra, Nikolaos Papadopoulos, Laura Ahumada-Arranz, Jakob El Kolthei, Barbra Treutlein, Johannes Soeding

Max Planck Institute for Biophysical Chemistry, DE

42 Structural characterization of the IC pocket in the human Cx50 hemichannel

Claudia Pareja-Barrueto, Jose Gomez, Felipe Villanelo, Peter Minogue, Viviana Berthoud, Eric Beyer, Tomas Perez-Acle

Computational Biology Laboratory (DLab), Fundacion Ciencia y Vida, CL

43 Automated gene annotation in non-model unicellular eukaryotic genomes

Loc Meunier, Loc Meunier, Damien Sirjacobs, Philippe Jacques, Denis Baurain

University of Liege, BE

44 Modeling and Stochastic Simulation of Gene Regulatory Networks in *Escherichia coli*

Rodrigo Santibez, Daniel Garrido, Toms Prez-Acle, Alberto J.M. Martin

Fundacin Ciencia Vida, CL

45 Drug Resistance Profiling of Malaria Parasitaemia using Biomedical Image Processing of Blood Sample Images

Eustache Muteba Ayumba

The International Medical Informatics Association (IMIA), CH

- 46** Problems with annotation and computational prediction of peptide amyloidogenicity
Micha Burdukiewicz, Stefan Rdiger, Marlena Gsior-Gogowska, Pawe Mackiewicz, Magorzata Kotulska
University of Wroclaw, PL
- 47** Genome-wide SNP analysis reveals distinct origins of *Trypanosoma evansi* and *Trypanosoma equiperdum*
Bart Cuypers, Frederik Van den Broeck, Nick Van Reet, Conor J. Meehan, Julien Cauchard, Jonathan M. Wilkes, Filip Claes, Bruno Goddeeris, Hadush Birhanu, Jean-Claude Dujardin, Kris Laukens, Philippe Bscher, Stijn Deborggraeve
Institute of Tropical Medicine, BE
- 48** Phylostratigraphic analyses of *Escherichia coli*
Hrvoje Mieti
Ruer Bokovi Institute, HR
- 49** RIP-MD: Generation and Analysis of Residue Interaction Networks in Molecular Dynamics of Proteins
Sebastian Contreras-Riquelme, Jose-Antonio Garate, Tomas Perez-Acle, Alberto J.M. Martin
Computational Biology Lab, Fundacion Ciencia y Vida, CL
- 50** Drug-target interaction prediction in drug repositioning and drug design
Daniele Parisi
KULeuven, BE
- 51** New binding site of the quorum sensing molecule N-3-Oxododecanoyl Homoserine Lactone with the transcriptional regulator LasR of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*: Insights from Molecular Docking and Dynamics Simulations
Grabski Hovakim, Lernik Hunanyan, Susanna Tiratsuyan, Hrachik Vardapetan
Russian-Armenian University, AM
- 52** The impact of native state switching on protein sequence evolution
Avital Sharir-Ivry, Yu Xia
McGill University, CA
- 53** Mining multiple pathogen-host interactomes for the detection of differentiating patterns
Pieter Moris, Pieter Meysman, Kris Laukens
UAntwerp, BE
- 54** MicrobiomeDB: a Web-based platform for interrogating microbiome experiments
Francislon S. Oliveira, Shon Cade, John Brestelli, John Iodice, Brian P. Brunk, Jie Zheng, Christian J. Stoeckert Jr, Gabriel R. Fernandes, Jessica C. Kissinger, David S. Roos, Daniel P. Beiting
Centro de Pesquisas Ren Rachou (Fiocruz Minas), BR
- 55** Comparative genomic, evolutionary and functional analysis of caleosins: a family of multi-functional plant and fungal proteins
Rahman Farzana, Mehedi Hassan, Rozana Rosli, Abdulsamie Hanano, Denis J Murphy
University of South Wales, GB
- 56** Robustness of modeling-based experiment retrieval to differences in measurement and pre-processing techniques
Pradeep Eranti, Paul Blomstedt, Samuel Kaski
Aalto University, FI

- 57** Computational methods for detection of allele specific expression and their diagnostic relevance for rare Mendelian disorders
Numrah Fadra, Eric Klee, Gavin Oliver
University of Minnesota, Mayo Clinic , US
- 58** Global proteomics profiling improves drug sensitivity prediction: results from a multi-omics, pan-cancer modeling approach
Mehreen Ali, Suleiman A. Khan, Krister Wennerberg, Tero Aittokallio
Institute for Molecular Medicine, University of Helsinki, FI
- 59** Computational proteogenomic identification of translated fusions and micro structural variations in cancer
Yen-Yi Lin, Lin, Alex Gawronski, Faraz Hach, Sujun Li, Ibrahim Numanagic, Iman Sarrafi, Swati Mishra, Andrew McPherson, Colin Collins Milan Radovich, Haixu Tang, S. Cenk Sahinalp
Simon Fraser University, CA
- 60** In Silico Identification and Screening of Compounds against the Identified Potential Drug Target of Resistant Mycobacterium tuberculosis
Noor-Ul-Ain Zahra, ReazUddin
University of Karachi, Karachi, PK
- 61** Core Proteome Mining of Pseudomonas aeruginosa to Identify Novel Drug Targets
Faiza Jamil, ReazUddin
University of Karachi, Karachi, PK
- 62** Additive Dose Response Models: Explicit Formulations and the Loewe Additivity Consistency Condition
Simone Lederer, Tjeerd Dijkstra, Tom Heskes
Radboud University, NL
- 63** Discovering genetic signatures of extreme physiology using African mole-rats
Ole Eigenbrod
Max Delbrueck Center for Molecular Medicine in the Helmholtz Society, DE
- 64** Novel Dog Genome Content Revealed by Pseudo-De Novo Assembly of Unmapped Sequence Reads
Meharji Arumilli, L. A. Holden, M. Hytonen, J. Salojrvi, H. T. Lohi, and K. H. Brown
University of Helsinki, FI
- 65** Standardisation and organisation of knowledge about neurodegenerative disease mechanisms for comparison over heterogeneous systems
Aishwarya Alex Namasivayam
University of Luxembourg, LU
- 66** NetRep: a scalable permutation approach for assessing replication and preservation of network modules in large datasets
Scott Ritchie, Stephen Watts, Liam G. Fearnley, Kathryn E. Holt, Gad Abraham, Michael Inouye
Baker Heart and Diabetes Research Institute, AU
- 67** RSG-Italy showcase activities
Lisanna Paladin, Marco Necci
Univerist degli Studi di Padova, IT

- 68** Proteins' Lengthy Variable Parts Modeling Using Global Optimization Algorithm with Coarse Grained Topology, Model Quality Assessment and Predicted Secondary Structure
Beomchang Kang
Seoul National University, KR
- 69** Unravelling the aromatic catabolism potential of the hydrocarbonoclastic marine bacterium *Alcaligenes sp.* QD168
Roberto Durán, Valentina Méndez, Francisco Salvà-Serra, Bárbara Barra, Edward Moore, Michael Seeger.
Universidad Técnica Federico Santa María, CL
- 70** Preprocessing of high-resolution mass spectrometry imaging data with optimized hierarchical agglomerative clustering (OHAC) and Bayesian statistics
Nazanin Zounemat Kermani
Imperial College London, GB
- 71** Transport pathways in membrane transport proteins.
Sayane Shome, Edward Yu, Robert Jernigan
Iowa State University, US
- 72** Formal description and reference implementation of a generic framework and a methodology for analysing molecular docking results
Damjan Temelkovski, Tamas Kiss, Gabor Terstyanszky, Pamela Greenwell
University of Westminster, GB
- 73** Engineering allostery using cell sorting and sequencing
John Koberstein
- 74** SMARTIV: A Novel Method for RNA Sequence and Structure Motif Discovery from In-vivo Binding Data
Maya Polishchuk
Technion - Israel Institute of Technology